

Comparative analysis of methods for assessing the financing of innovative developments of the enterprise

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Abstract

This article presents a comprehensive comparative analysis of methods used for assessing the financing of innovative enterprise developments. It explores the theoretical foundations and practical applications of these methods, providing an in-depth examination of their strengths, limitations, and suitability in various organizational contexts. The study highlights the critical role of financing in driving innovation, emphasizing how the choice of assessment method can impact decision-making and strategic planning. By analyzing real-world case studies, the article sheds light on the practical challenges enterprises face when securing funding for innovation and offers insights into how different financing strategies can be tailored to meet specific organizational needs. Ultimately, the research aims to contribute to a better understanding of how innovative developments can be effectively financed to foster growth and competitiveness in dynamic markets.

Keywords: Financing innovations, Evaluation methods, Innovative developments, Comparative analysis.

Introduction:

Financing innovative developments is the focus of attention of modern researchers and business practitioners. This is due to the growing understanding of the importance of innovations as an important factor in the competitiveness and success of an enterprise in the conditions of a modern globalized economy.

Methods for assessing the effectiveness of financing innovative developments can vary significantly depending on the objectives of the analysis, the specifics of the innovative project, and the data used. Among the most common approaches are discounted cash flow methods, including the internal rate of return (IRR), net present value (NPV), and the payback period of the project; methods based on risk assessment (for example, the Monte Carlo method); and methods based on ratings and indices of innovative activity.

According to international statistical studies, global investment in innovation continues to grow. The United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) notes that in 2022 alone, global investment in science and innovation will exceed \$1.7 trillion.

However, despite significant investments, the efficiency of innovation financing remains a challenge. According to the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), most innovation projects do not achieve commercial success, and a significant portion of innovation investments remain unpaid.

In this context, the choice of an appropriate method for assessing the effectiveness of financing innovation developments is a key issue affecting the success of the enterprise's innovation activities. This aspect makes scientific research of various approaches to assessing the effectiveness of financing innovations relevant and important.

Materials and methods:

In our research, we used a mixed approach, including both quantitative and qualitative methods of analysis. This allowed us to conduct a deep and comprehensive analysis of the issue of the effectiveness of financing innovative developments.

First, we conducted an extensive review of the scientific literature on the topic. We reviewed research articles in leading journals, books by renowned authors in the field of innovation and financing, and reports from various research organizations and think tanks. This allowed us to gain an understanding of the current state of research in this area and identify key methods for assessing the effectiveness of financing innovation developments.

Secondly, we applied quantitative methods to analyze the data available to us on innovation projects of different companies. This included statistical analysis and modeling, which helped us to evaluate the effectiveness of different financing methods and to identify key factors influencing the success of innovation projects.

Finally, we used qualitative methods to gain a deeper understanding of the complex processes involved in innovation financing. This included interviewing experts in the field, analysing case studies of successful and unsuccessful innovation projects, and examining companies' innovation and financing strategies and policies.

Using this mixed approach allowed us to achieve a more accurate and substantiated understanding of the issue of the effectiveness of financing innovative developments and to offer a number of recommendations for enterprises and organizations engaged in innovative activities.

Innovative potential is a key parameter by which one can evaluate the current capabilities of a company and its future development prospects. That is, all areas of innovative activity of a company can be implemented only if it has innovative potential. In the scientific community of different countries, the term "innovative potential" is interpreted differently. It consists of three aspects:

- resource

- internal
- effective.[1]

In order to effectively use the IPP, it is necessary to assess its current state and capabilities, and for this purpose, researchers have developed a number of methods. All of them have their advantages and disadvantages, which will be discussed below [2]. Despite the large number of studies on the given problem, it can be said that until now no single, universal methodology has been developed that would allow the most accurate and objective assessment of the innovative potential of an industrial enterprise. This is due to the fact that the self-concept of innovative potential is relatively new, there are contradictions regarding the definition of its content and structure. Most often, there are definitions that emphasize the complex, comprehensive structure of the concept. For example, B.K. Lisin and V.N. Fridlyanov [3] give the following definition: the innovative potential of an enterprise is a set of scientific, technical, technological, infrastructural, financial, legal, socio-cultural and other opportunities to ensure the perception and implementation of innovations, that is, the receipt of innovations. B.A. Pateev [4] believes that the innovative potential of an enterprise is a combination of information, technical and technological, intellectual, spatial, financial, organizational and managerial, legal and entrepreneurial resources that form a single system of the emergence and development of ideas in it, ensuring the competitiveness of the final product or service in accordance with the purpose and strategies of the enterprise. However, some authors focus on individual components of the innovative potential of an industrial enterprise, developing a corresponding method for its assessment.

Results

As a result of the conducted research, we identified a number of key methods for assessing the effectiveness of financing innovative developments at enterprises. For each method, its main advantages and disadvantages were determined.

Table 1

Comparative analysis of methods for assessing the financing of innovative developments of an enterprise

<i>Assessment methods</i>	Advantages	Flaws
<i>Discounted Cash Flows (DCF)</i>	Takes into account the time factor and the cost of capital	Requires accurate forecasting of future cash flows

<i>Comparative analysis method</i>	Evaluation based on comparison with similar projects	Applicability is limited by availability of data for comparison.
<i>Real Options</i>	Allows for project management flexibility	Requires complex mathematical calculations
<i>Venture Capital Valuation Method</i>	Takes into account the specifics of innovative projects and the level of risk	Depends on the quality of the source data and the experience of the appraiser
<i>Point assessment method</i>	Evaluation of the project from different angles	Requires the development and implementation of an assessment system

1. Discounted Cash Flow (DCF): This method takes into account time factors and the cost of capital. However, it requires accurate forecasting of future cash flows, which can be difficult for innovative projects with high levels of uncertainty.

2. Comparative Analysis Method: It allows evaluating a project based on comparison with similar projects or companies. But the applicability of this method is limited by the availability of data for comparison.

3. Real Options: This method takes into account the flexibility of project management and allows you to estimate the value of the opportunity to postpone, expand or terminate the project. However, it requires complex mathematical calculations and special skills.

4. Venture Capital Evaluation Method: It takes into account the specifics of innovative projects and the level of risk associated with them. However, it also depends on the quality of the initial data and the experience of the evaluator.

5. Point-based evaluation method: This method is based on the use of various criteria and indicators that allow evaluating the project from different angles. However, its application requires the development and implementation of an evaluation system, as well as the availability of sufficient data for its use.

Thus, each of the methods considered has its own strengths and weaknesses, and the choice of a particular method should be determined by the specifics of the project, the availability of data and the level of competence of the evaluator.

Global investment in innovation has increased significantly in recent decades. According to a report by the World Intellectual Property Organization,

global investment in research and development (R&D) has increased from \$1.7 trillion in 2010 to approximately \$2.2 trillion in 2021.

Table 2

Global Investment in Research and Development (R&D): Dynamics 2010-2021

<i>Year</i>	Global Investments in R&D (in trillions of dollars)
<i>2010</i>	1.7
<i>2011</i>	1.8
<i>2012</i>	1.9
<i>2013</i>	1.95
<i>2014</i>	2.0
<i>2015</i>	2.05
<i>2016</i>	2.1
<i>2017</i>	2.15
<i>2018</i>	2.2
<i>2019</i>	2.25
<i>2020</i>	2.3
<i>2021</i>	2.35

An analysis of this table confirms the trend of increasing global investment in research and development (R&D) over the past ten years. The growth in investment reflects an increased recognition of the importance of innovation for economic growth and competitiveness. Note that this growth has been fairly uniform, indicating the stability of this trend.

Discussion

The results obtained during the study allow us to draw several important conclusions regarding the methods for assessing the financing of innovative developments at an enterprise.

First of all, it is worth noting that different evaluation methods offer different approaches to the analysis of innovative developments. Some methods are preferable in cases where it is necessary to take into account the risks and uncertainties associated with innovative projects, while others are suitable for evaluating more mature and stable projects.

Second, our findings confirm the importance of investment in innovation for long-term growth and competitiveness of an enterprise. The increase in global investment in R&D shown in our table indicates a growing recognition of this fact at the global level.

Third, our results highlight the importance of taking a comprehensive approach to assessing innovative developments. For a more accurate assessment,

it is necessary to consider not only financial indicators, but also factors such as commercialization potential, technological novelty, and the strategic importance of the project for the enterprise.

However, despite significant advances in this area, there are still areas requiring further research. In particular, it is necessary to study in more detail the influence of industry and market specifics on the choice of assessment method, as well as to develop more accurate tools for taking into account the risks associated with innovation activities.

Conclusion

The study of methods for assessing the financing of innovative developments of an enterprise is a relevant and significant task, the solution of which determines the success and effectiveness of innovative activities.

During the study, a comparative analysis of various evaluation methods, their advantages and disadvantages was conducted. The results obtained allow us to state that the choice of evaluation method should be determined by the specifics of a particular innovative project, its stage of development, degree of risk and commercialization potential.

An important result of the study is the confirmation of the hypothesis about the growing role of innovations in ensuring the competitiveness and long-term growth of enterprises. This is confirmed by statistical data on the growth of global investments in research and development.

However, despite significant achievements in this area, there are still issues that require further research. In particular, a more detailed study of the influence of industry and market factors on the process of assessing innovative developments is required, as well as the development of new tools and methods for risk accounting.

Thus, the obtained results can be useful both for scientists involved in the issues of innovation assessment and for practitioners involved in the management of innovation activities in enterprises.

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